

Magnetic Study of Mixed Crystals of System S—Se.

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The magnetic properties of binary systems with metallic components which either form continuous solid solutions or are partially miscible, have already been studied by various workers (*cf.* Honda and Sone, *Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1913, 2, 1; Endo, *ibid.*, 1925, 14, 479; Garrison, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 622; Spencer and John, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, A 116, 61), and that of binary system of salts has been studied by the present authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 347). So far as the authors are aware a binary system with non-metallic components has not been studied from this point of view, therefore the study of the magnetic property of S—Se system, a non-metallic one, forms the subject of the present investigation.

From phase-diagram point of view the system has been studied by Rathke (*Annalen*, 1869, 152, 188) and later on by Rath and Bettendes (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1879, 139, 329); but it was thoroughly investigated by Ringer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 32, 183). He found that melted Se and liquid sulphur can be mixed in all proportions, but it is very difficult to crystallise it out when Se content is more than 10%. In the present investigation, therefore, the magnetic property of mixed crystals, whose Se content does not exceed 10%, has only been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphur, from which the mixed crystals were prepared was the purest obtainable and further purified by crystallisation from pure carbon disulphide. Selenium was available in the form which was insoluble in CS₂; therefore the soluble form was prepared by dissolving the available variety in HNO₃ and HCl and by reducing the selenious acid thus formed to red amorphous Se by SO₂. Se thus formed was filtered, washed thoroughly with alcohol and was dried in an electric oven maintained at 40°. Before use the purity of the

elements was further tested by determining their melting points and specific gravities which are given in Table I and for comparison the values given in books are added in parenthesis.

FIG. 1.

S—Se System.

TABLE I.

Substance.	M. p.	Sp. gr.
Rhombic sulphur	113° (115°)	2.04 (2.037)
Red selenium	215° (212-217°)	4.39 (4.36)

The thermal method of preparing the mixed crystals was not resorted to in order to avoid any complication that may arise on account of chemical transformation, such as oxide formation and the appearance of the phenomenon of allotropic modification at high temperatures, but the mixed crystals of S—Se were prepared by precipitation from CS_2 solution. Saturated solutions, both of S and

Se, were prepared in hot CS₂ and were mixed in different proportions. The solvent was allowed to evaporate gradually and the crystals that separated were quickly filtered off and dried with filter paper. These crystals were placed in an oven maintained at 40-45° for a number of hours in order to get rid of any CS₂ that might be sticking to the crystals, and after that the crystals were placed in a vacuum desiccator till further use. The crystals thus obtained were all rhombic resembling the sulphur crystals but their colour varied from dark-red to brown-red. The samples got in this way were analysed for Se and S, both by dissolving them in HNO₃ and a small quantity of bromine. Sulphur was estimated from the solution by the usual SO₄ method and Se by reducing selenious acid thus formed by hydroxylamine hydrochloride to red amorphous Se.

Data for the densities of the samples as determined are given in Fig. 1, and in Table II.

TABLE II.

Density of the mixed crystals.

(Se) %	...	0	1.19	4.10	7.25	13.36	15.57	17.42	20.71	100
Density (obs.)		2.04	2.09	2.18	2.25	2.40	2.455	2.51	2.58	4.39
Density (calc.)			2.06	2.13	2.21	2.35	2.405	2.449	2.52	—

The magnetic susceptibility of mixed crystals was determined by the magnetic balance of the Wilson type which was used in our previous work.

Pure water which has a mass susceptibility of -7.2×10^{-7} was used as the comparison substance in all determinations.

Susceptibility of the pure components.—The mass and the atomic susceptibility of the pure element, from which the mixed crystals were obtained are given in Table III and for comparison values obtained by others workers are added.

TABLE III.

Element.	Observed.		Other workers.	
	$\chi \times 10^7$.	$\chi_{at} \times 10^7$.	$\chi \times 10^7$	$\chi_{at} \times 10^7$.
Rhombic sulphur	-5.08	-162.9	-5.1 (Curie) -4.9 (Pascal)	-160.0 (Bhatnagar and Dhawan)
Selenium	-3.04	-240.7	-3.04 (Honda and Sone) -3.1 (Curie)	-235.0 (Pascal) -254.0 (Bhatnagar and Dhawan)

The values of susceptibility with composition of the mixed crystals and of mechanical mixture are tabulated in Table IV and the curve plotted is given in Fig. 1.

TABLE IV.

	Wt %	Atom % Se.	$\chi \times 10^7$ Mixed crystals.	Atomic wt.	$\chi_{me}, -10^7$ Mixed crystals.	Mechanical mixture.
A.	1.19	0.48	-5.09	32.32	-164.5	-163.1
B.	4.10	1.70	-5.11	32.86	-167.9	-164.1
C.	7.25	3.06	-5.06	33.50	-169.5	-165.2
D.	13.36	5.88	-4.92	34.85	-171.5	-167.6
E.	15.57	6.90	-4.87	35.31	-171.8	-168.1
F.	17.42	7.86	-4.81	35.76	-172.0	-168.8
G.	20.71	9.50	-4.74	36.52	-172.8	-170.0

DISCUSSION.

In discussing the results the following factors have to be taken into consideration.

(a) *Effect of impurities.*—Spencer and John (*loc. cit.*) observed that magnetic susceptibility of alloys of elements particularly of Pb and Hg, which form mere mechanical mixtures of Pb and Hg in all proportions, did not show a linear relation between susceptibility and concentration as it should have; but on the other hand so marked were the deviations that alloys containing 3.6% to 47.6% by weight of lead were found to be strongly paramagnetic notwithstanding the fact that both pure lead and silver are diamagnetic. Montgomery and Ross (*Phys. Rev.*, 1933, **43**, 358) have, however, very recently observed that magnetic susceptibility of lead and silver alloys does vary linearly with composition and suggest that the departures from linear relation observed by Spencer and John (*loc. cit.*) are on account of iron contamination.

In the present investigation, therefore, special precautions were taken to ensure the purity of the components as well as of the mixed crystals. Various physical properties, such as density, melting point, and magnetic susceptibility of the elements were determined

before use and the specimens having values corresponding to those given in standard books were only used. CS_2 could be the only possible impurity in the mixed crystals. This impurity was kept out by maintaining the oven at $40\text{--}45^\circ$ temperature which is the boiling point of CS_2 . They were further placed in a vacuum desiccator.

(b) *Effect of absorbed gasses.*—Shimizu (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 826) has recently shown that in most cases the rapid decrease of magnetic susceptibility of an element like Bi, or Sb on the addition of an element like Sn, Te or Pb was not due to the formation of solid solution between the two elements, as was previously supposed, but was due to the absorbed gases in alloys. Alloys are generally prepared by heating the components to high temperature and then allowing the mass to cool. It is during this process of cooling that various gases are absorbed. In this system of S—Se the possibility of gases being absorbed is remote because the mixed crystals have been prepared at ordinary temperatures out of solution and not at high temperatures employed in the preparation of the alloys.

Moreover, if the gases had been absorbed then the value of the susceptibility would have decreased but on the other hand we find that the values had actually increased. From the table it is clear that if the concentration-susceptibility graph be plotted, then the curve will not follow the linear path which it would have were it to obey the simple additive law of Pascal for mixtures, but it follows a curved path. The maximum deviation from the additive value has been found to occur at a point where S and Se exist in a ratio 32:1. It is well known that both S and Se exist in various molecular complexes as S_8 , Se_8 , Se_{16} , Se_{32} .

The crystal pattern of sulphur consists of 128 atoms of sulphur. The deviation from the additive law, therefore, would appear to be due to the formation of S—Se complexes which may be represented by the general formula $\text{S}_x \text{Se}_y$ where x and y are any numbers.

